

The human right to health: Empathy and universal human dignity versus apathetic capitalism

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Abstract

The human right to health as a concept continues to face many challenges. The ineffective role of the World Health Organization in previous decades and the rise of neoliberal capitalism have contributed significantly to the "shaky foundations" of the human right to health and the "conventional reluctance" to accept the so-called broad understanding of health, depicted in this paper as the social determination of health. This concept means that health (like positive and negative health outcomes) results from structural, racial, and class differences. On the other hand, the separation of reason and emotions in today's prevailing positivistic epistemology in social sciences is another crucial factor in the slow development of the human right to health. This separation has manifested itself in human rights studies by overlooking the concept of empathy in legitimizing the universality of human rights, even though empathy is a critical concept in understanding the universal moral dignity of human beings. Furthermore, these epistemological problems are compounded by the capitalist ethos, which leads to the hardening of personality and an empathy gap that contributes to the challenges in developing the human right to health. Empathy is necessary to understand health's social determination and fully develop the human right to health, but positivistic social sciences and capitalism-driven reason undermine it.

Take-home message: Policymakers are urged to integrate empathy and a broader understanding of health determinants into their strategies to ensure the universal realization of health rights and address the underlying social and economic disparities.

Keywords: Capitalism; empathy; health; human rights; human dignity; human right to health.

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INTRODUCTION

Human rights are conceived as instruments that enable people to lead a life of dignity, be free and equal citizens, make meaningful choices, and pursue their life plans [1]. However, there are still many challenges to human rights (including the difficulties in conceptualizing the human right to health, which is the central theme of this paper) that do not necessarily emanate from tyrants, dictators, and autocrats. Many fundamental challenges to human rights arise from capitalism. A shining example

is the difficulties in substantiating the existence and full-fledged development of the human right to health (and, by extension, the human right to health care).

For the last decades, the health systems of many developed and developing countries have been privatized and commercialized, and social protection has also been thinned out due to the reforms promoted by the neoliberal agenda that has gained dominance in the global political economy and in the decision-making processes of major international financial institutions. As a result, the population's health has fundamentally deteriorated, as emphasized by British [2] and Italian [3] scholars. The consequences of the recent COVID-19 pandemic show how deep this problem runs. It can be argued that the impact of the pandemic has been devastating due to neoliberal reforms of previous decades, which harmed social protection. However, health is a matter of social well-being; health is a matter of power relations besides mental and physical well-being [1,4].

On the other hand, Jonathan Wolff [5], one of the leading advocates of the human right to health, pointed out in 2012 that although the human right to health was established in international law in 1976, philosophers have tended to view human rights doctrine as a marginal contribution to political philosophy or have attempted to distinguish “human rights proper” from “aspirations,” with the human right to health often considered as falling into the latter category. Similarly, Tobin [6] noted that the human right to health has been viewed as a right with “shaky conceptual foundations” or an “incompletely conceptualized” right. O’Connell [7] stated that the right to health can be seen as one of the most subversive human rights. This paper argues that this is due to the pitfalls of today's prevailing positivistic epistemology, characterized by the separation of reason from emotion, and even promotes what some scholars call “lop-sided reason” [8].

As an interdisciplinary and conceptual normative, this paper has two central objectives: (1) to shed light on the human right to health by discussing the broad concept of health, and (2) to consider the place of empathy in developing a fully-fledged human right to health. Conceptually, this paper shares the critical realist approach's critique of positivism in social sciences. The positivistic approach in social sciences emulates the natural sciences by emphasizing the scientific method, such as logical reasoning and empirical experience, as the only sources of knowledge. The positivistic framework tends to see the world as deterministic, which operates by laws of cause and effect that can be discerned. If positivism regards the so-called objective knowledge of society as something possible, however, the normative visions of morality and ethics are accepted as subjective and irrational [9,10]

Overall, this paper aims to raise awareness about the importance of empathy, a crucial concept for developing human rights to health and health care and, in general, for legitimizing the universality of human rights. Empathy is necessary to accept the human rights to health and health care as part of the universalistic nature of human rights, the defining characteristic of which is to belong to all. On the other hand, we need heart (empathy) to fully perceive the broadly understood concept of health, which implies the social determination of health. However, the so-called “lop-sided reason” of capitalism and positivistic epistemology impedes it.

The rest of this article is structured as follows. First, the broad understanding of health, the problematic development of the human right to health, and the problems caused by neoliberal capitalism in social protection and health-related issues are touched on. Next, the concept of the social determination of health is explored. Then, the concept of empathy that legitimizes universal human dignity and the factors leading to its erosion and hardening of personality are discussed in connection with neoliberal capitalism and the epistemological problems of positivistic social sciences. Finally, this paper attempts to theorize how to substantiate and develop the human right to health. In doing so, the arguments for the need to accept the concept of care as a human being's relationship to the world, to accept that emotions are not beyond reason, and the need for “truly universal human rights” are presented.

DISCUSSION

Health as a polysemic concept and the broad understanding of health

The 1946 WHO Constitution defined health as “a complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”. This initial definition of health is inclusive and broad and indicates that health and well-being are closely related concepts [4]. The notion of health has evolved over the last decades. As such, biological, psychosocial, environmental, socio-economical, health behavior practices, medical advancement, and ecological determinants are different determinants of health [11]. Also, factors such as class and racial inequality, employment, education, and housing are social determinants of overarching importance for health [1]. In other words, health has to be understood broadly in line with the so-called bio-psycho-social model, and according to the conceptualization of Muyskens [12], health consists of four interrelated components: biological, psychological, social, and environmental.

Because of the nexus between human, animal, and ecosystem health, a trans-disciplinary approach called “One Health” was introduced in 2003–2004. It aims to achieve optimal health outcomes by considering the interconnections in our shared environment [13]. The concept of “One Health” is crucial to developing a broad understanding of health (accepting that health has, *inter alia*, social and environmental determinants) rather than a narrowly defined one centered around mere bio-medical understanding.

Health is a socio-economically, hence, politically, ecologically determined polysemic phenomenon. Broadly understood health goes beyond health care, including the ecological, social, economic, and political factors that shape and influence health. What human rights treaty supervisory bodies, foremost the WHO, largely overlooked for decades is that a bio-psycho-social model that recognizes the potential of social factors, not just pathological conditions, should have been used to define the concept of health and right to health [6].

The problematic development of the human right to health: WHO's ineffective role in previous decades

The WHO Constitution, which regulated health within the UN framework, operationalized human rights to public health and proclaimed for the first time that “the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being” [14].

Nonetheless, a close examination of the functioning of the WHO, the main international institution with a mandate to develop global public health, reveals a mixed record in developing a broad understanding of health and establishing human rights to health and health care. Initially, the WHO was enthusiastically involved in shaping what was conceived as “the right to the highest attainable standard of health.” However, it then entered a phase where it sought to avoid active engagement with human rights [15]. The WHO almost completely distanced itself from its earlier commitment to international health rights; moreover, it actively declined to participate in the ongoing formulation of the right to health in international legal documents [16]. Although the WHO attempted to implement the “Health for All” strategy adopted in the 1978 Alma-Ata Declaration, these efforts proved unsuccessful due to the global advance of the neoliberal economic paradigm in the following decades [17].

Around the turn of the millennium, the United Nations attempted to interpret the right to health in a way consistent with public health principles by formulating a commitment to address the “fundamental determinants of health”. Therefore, the WHO also sought to establish health-related rights within the framework of global health law [14]. In recent years, the WHO has moved in a [human] rights-friendly direction, recognizing the role of social determinants in health conditions. For example, a WHO factsheet published in 2017 states: “Understanding health as a human right obliges states to ensure access to timely, acceptable and affordable health care of adequate quality and to provide for the underlying determinants of health” [18]. Although the UN and the WHO have tried to move towards a rights-based approach and recognize the role of the social determinants of health, their ways of working are still ineffective in formulating a broad understanding of health and developing full-fledged human rights to health and health care. The main reason is that most of the proposed policy prescriptions and new

initiatives, even the Sustainable Development Goals, fell short of a serious reappraisal of the current capitalist system, which is the primary factor behind both intra-state and inter-state inequality, injustice, and coloniality, as well impossibility to implement structurally inclusive development [19,20]. In other words, most of the fundamental challenges to human rights, the protection of health, and the creation of truly inclusive development models arise from capitalism, which, with a focus on social policies, is analyzed next.

Thinning of social state, health, and neoliberal capitalism

The means of domination, exploitation, and destruction in the modern capitalistic society may be more sophisticated and may be less direct than outright slavery. Still, domination continues with ever greater global consequences [21]. The adverse effects of neoliberal capitalism on health in general and the development of human rights to health and health care in particular have been widely discussed [2,3,22]. Privatization and the accompanying commercialization of health care have taken on an increasing role in providing health care services in states in recent decades. Neoliberal capitalism is the primary force behind the commercialization of health care. It has turned health care and medical care into a privileged sphere of capital accumulation and super-profits - at the expense of individual human rights to health and health care, including in the public health sector [22]. Injustice in health-related issues is evident in the commodification and commercialization of healthcare systems, which violently curtail the vital potential of healthcare by limiting its benefits only to select groups of people [16]. This contributes to creating and perpetuating social injustice, which in the neoliberal capitalist system leads to structural injustice and violence due to systemic social and class inequalities.

Neoliberal capitalism negates social justice since it accepts the social programs, allegedly, as a sign of the totalitarian mind [23]. In the neoliberal view, social programs violate the rule of law [24]. Neoliberalism appears not simply as a set of arguments used “against universal health care, but rather a discourse that shapes all major discussions of the welfare state” [25], and it gives the opponents of the welfare state ammunition against any increases in the role of government in social protection [25]. Overall, since neoliberal capitalism creates social and structural injustice and violence, the conditions for the violations of human rights to health and health care are structurally embedded in neoliberal capitalism’s mindset, which is specifically inimical to the realization of social and economic rights [24,26].

Contrary to neoliberal assumptions, social justice and people’s health are directly linked [22]. Furthermore, protecting human dignity in our time requires institutionalized social protection and the creation of a social welfare state [27]. As such, one of the critical goals of welfare state measures, which is to end dependence on and the need for assistance and to restore or enable autonomy, is demanded by the human dignity of the recipients of assistance [27]. Nevertheless, the view that connects welfare, the protection of economic and social rights, and human dignity is still relatively weak in the social sciences.

Following the logic of Peterlini [28], neoliberal reforms have created “institutional cruelization” in social protection, health care, and health-related issues in general. In the aftermath of the pandemic, we can speak of a whole series of failures to achieve the universal health coverage promoted by the United Nations and the World Health Organization (WHO) as part of the Sustainable Development Goals [29]. These problems are also rooted in the systemic and structural problems created and perpetuated by neoliberal capitalism and its recent modifications. “Social determination of health”, which the following subsection explores, is a vital concept to unpack the systemic and structural injustice created by neoliberal capitalism.

Social determination of health and “conventional reluctance”

The so-called conventional public health practitioners and epidemiologists focused primarily on the influence of so-called “risk factors”, which are about living and working conditions. In doing so, they eclipsed the broad understanding of health, which considers the social determination of health [30]. However, for many years, the pioneers of social epidemiology emphasized that it is impossible to overlook the nexus between biological-physiological and socio-political determinants of health. Krieger [31] noted that “biological expressions of social inequality refer to how people literally embody and biologically

express experiences of economic and social inequality, from womb to death, thereby producing social inequalities in health across a wide range of outcomes”. For example, children’s health and development outcomes are related to their families' social and economic conditions; the higher up the socioeconomic spectrum, the better the outcomes [32].

In general, health inequalities are not just a matter of economic disparities and differences between rich and poor, men and women, but a more complex phenomenon. Inequality and discrimination should be understood as multidimensional: social class, gender, race, ethnicity, or generational difference. It is important to avoid simplistic analyses when we deconstruct the social aspects to fully understand and deal with health inequalities. We must uncover how social inequalities that lead to health disparities are created and maintained [33].

Health inequalities require an intersectional approach that accepts that inequalities intersect simultaneously [33]. Jaime Breilh [4], in advocating a transdisciplinary approach to health, points out that variables such as the social and economic determinants of health only acquire meaning and status concerning the political and social context that determines them and the analytical node they form. Overall, the narrow definitions of health based on a bio-medical or bio-statistical understanding separate the concept of health from well-being, social and political factors and fail to implement the full-fledged right to health.

The COVID-19 pandemic highlights the dangers of a narrow understanding of health and not accepting human rights to health and health care. Pandemic eloquently proved the analysis of Yamin [1], holding that adverse health outcomes should be viewed not only through the prism of bio-medical risk factors but also through the prism of social-economic, structural, racial, and class inequalities. Overall, the concept of social determination of health means that social and economic dynamics seriously affect population health. Moreover, the social determination of health and its amenability makes health political. Biomedical reductionism should be criticized in the context of social determination and ecological determinants of health (the environmental determinants of health are the necessary complements to the social determinants of health).

On the other hand, a broad understanding of health lays the grounds for developing full-fledged right to health and accepting that health care is a human right. In essence, health care is about the human rights to life and security. The means to enjoy the right to health care should be accessible to all population groups, without distinction as to economic class, social status, gender, and physical location [7]. However, “conventional reluctance” to accept the social determination of health impedes the development of the human right to health and, by extension, the human right to health care. There is a need for empathy to understand the social determinants of health, which is discussed next.

Empathy, the universality of human rights, and the human right to health

Empathy is commonly associated with benevolence, pity, or sympathy [34]. In feeling empathy, it is important to accept a willingness to be affected and shaped by another’s experiences without blurring the lines between the self and the other [35]. In other words, empathy does not necessarily lead to unipathy [34]. Following the logic of Brown [36], empathy can be understood as taking perspectives, refraining from judgment, recognizing others' emotions, and communicating recognition of others’ emotions.

It is argued that human rights need heart, not (ir)rational norms. With reason, and thus with “rationally generated” norms, everything can be “rationalized”, even genocide [37]. As Barreto [38] points out, “Modern rationalism is not the emancipation of the individual from all tutors, but the submission of the individual to the masters of aggression and cruelty”. Therefore, the importance of empathy to human rights engagement was fundamentally disregarded, and normative questions about the relationship between empathy and human rights were largely neglected [39]. In other words, since human rights have been usually conceived through an appeal to reason, empathy has been overlooked in human rights studies [39]. All in all, within the context of the dominant rationalist philosophical and legal culture, the relationship between morality and emotions and human rights and feelings cannot be seen [38].

Lynn Hunt [40], in her seminal book on the origins and foundations of human rights in empathy, states that not only the definition of human rights but, foremost, their very existence depends as much on emotion as on reason. Particularly, "imagined empathy" (in the sense that empathy requires belief and feeling that others are like us) is the foundation of human rights. [40]. Bendik-Keymer [41] asserts that human rights are based on the idea that every human being has dignity, and if there is a logic to this extension of dignity, it comes from the growth of empathy. "It is through empathy and less through pure reason that another person is perceived as equal – equal in the sense of being an equally sentient being" [37].

Overall, the inclusion of empathy, which allows us to resonate with the pain, distress, affect, and emotional state of others, enables a proper reconstruction of human rights principles and norms and fills the gaps that traditional human rights theories have ignored — the consideration of emotions, altruism, and human nature [39]. Empathy is necessary to recognize that an important dimension of the human experience that shapes health is determined by social relationships and ethnic, racial, and class identities [1]. Overall, empathy is vital to legitimize the universality of human rights and human rights to health and health care. However, empathy is a capacity that needs to be developed. Its lack and erosion are socially created, discussed in the next section.

Erosion of empathy, hardening of personality, and apathetic rationalism of neoliberal capitalism

While natural and universal, the human faculties to empathize and sympathize are also relatively weak and in constant danger of being suppressed and overridden by fear, hatred, cruelty, or ideology [39]. Intuitive sharing of others' emotional and motivational states, the most basic mechanism of empathy, is constrained by socially constructed biases [42]. The more prejudiced people are, the less likely they are to intuitively grasp the emotional states of others. Thus, the brain effects associated with less empathic responses are a function of culture, education, and acquired norms rather than innate preferences. [42]. The unconditional belief in a self-regulating market (neoliberal ideology plays an important role today by presenting itself as a kind of "common sense") can be seen as a socially learned "cultural bias" that can impair empathy. The capitalist logic presented as "universal" market rules not only generates inequality but also provides the basis for socially constructed cultural biases. In other words, the empathy gap for the "other" (e.g., those who are less well-off) arises because of prejudices that are a logical outcome of neoliberal logic and education that informs the belief in the "universality" of market rules.

Hardening of personality has a genealogical link to the authoritarian character, characterized by a lack of certain positive emotions [38]. This authoritarian character also describes the market society, where the market rules are authoritarian and uncompromising. According to Lakoff [43], an authoritarian character describes unregulated capitalism or neoliberalism as being the embodiment of the so-called "strict parent", who is authoritarian, unempathetic, despotic, and can punish those who do not follow the rules of the market.

The hardening of personality (as indifference to the suffering of others) under market rules can explain indifference to the human suffering caused by the curtailment, abrogation, or thinning of social and economic rights, which are directly related to health. Suppose the profit-oriented practical reason or the apathetic rationality of neoliberal capitalism shapes the understanding of health and penetrates the healthcare sector. In that case, this will lead to the deterioration and violation of not only social and economic rights but also fundamental rights such as the right to life and security. To conclude, capitalism ruptures connections and destroys empathy and caring.

Separation of reason and emotions, empathy gap, "capitalistic coldness," and challenges to develop human rights

This paper argues that it is crucial to understand the capitalist "morality" and culture as one of apathy, which leads to hardness or hardening of personality [38]. According to the interpretation of Adorno and Horkheimer by Barreto [38], the virtue of apathy is to overcome compassion and to do everything without any feeling. The concept of hardness can be used to explain the indifference toward human pain and suffering under the so-called market rules, which, inter alia, can justify the

curtailment and abrogation of social and economic rights, many of which are health-related. What “capitalist coldness” can yield, to paraphrase Barreto [38], is the discredit of sympathy for fellow human beings and moral emotions.

“Capitalistic coldness” has a direct nexus with the modern positivistic epistemology, which, if not dichotomizes but, at least, separates reason and emotions. In this regard, Barreto [38] points out that modern positivist morality is hampered by a solipsistic rationalism that lacks an account of the participation of emotions in moral life. The separation of reason and emotions is a serious epistemological problem of today's positivistic social sciences. In human rights studies, it has manifested itself in overlooking empathy in legitimizing human rights universality [37,40]. Also, the relatively weak foundations of the human right to health that Wolff [5] notes due to the decades-long tendency (since the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights) among philosophers to view human rights doctrine as a marginal contribution to political philosophy is an eloquent expression of this epistemological problem of positivistic social sciences.

As it can be seen, neoliberal capitalist morality is hampered by solipsistic rationalism and a coldness that disregards the participation of positive feelings in moral life. Moreover, this rationalism and coldness discredit compassion and moral feelings (all these inevitably affect the development of human rights to health and health care). However, a careful reading of Adam Smith, the founder of modern capitalist economics, can show that he emphasized attention to the well-being of others, which Sayer [44] argues implies empathy. Sugden [45] reminds us that Smith's position on how people's feelings affect each other points to a “fellow feeling” that does not fit within the ontological framework of rational choice theory. Therefore, modern readers of Smith tend to overlook it and try to explain everything through positivistic methods and one-sided rationalism.

The empathy gap is manifested in the reluctance to accept the broad understanding of health, which includes the social needs of the people and encompasses power relations in society. Thus, neoliberal capitalism not only creates and sustains structural inequality and injustice, which leads to poor health outcomes but also contributes to the empathy gap, a factor hindering the full-fledged development of the human right to health. Overall, the erosion of empathy and the emergence of an empathy gap in market societies should be analyzed in the context of the difficulties in developing the right to health and recognizing health care as a human right.

Substantiating the human right to health: Overcoming the separation of reason and emotions and acceptance of concern as human beings' relation to the world

As critical realist scholar Sayer [44,46,47] emphasizes, our relationship with the world is one of concern. The normal condition of the human psyche is the connection, first of all, to our loved ones [48]. Connection is about being concerned and empathetic. However, positivistic philosophy and social sciences fail to recognize that human's relationship to the world is one of concern [46,47]. Logically, the literature on social ontology rarely moves beyond discussions of structure and agency and largely fails to recognize that humans are needy and vulnerable social beings [47]. Specifically, feminist ethics points out that philosophy's male bias prevents it from understanding ordinary life and the place of care, especially women's moral experience, by universalizing men's morality in a patriarchal but liberal context [46,49]. However, humans are inherently evaluative beings. They must constantly monitor and evaluate how they and the things they care about are faring and decide what to do about it because human psychology is inherently vulnerable. Humans are dependent on other beings [47].

On the other hand, emotions such as concern about others, care, and empathy are not entirely unreasonable [44,46]. Following norms recklessly and without empathy would be considered “unreasonable” [44]. In English, (un)ethical behavior or persons are represented as “(un)reasonable” not only in the sense that people (do not) listen to reason but also that they pay close attention to the well-being of those with whom they deal and are sensitive to the needs and vulnerabilities of others. It is an ethical judgment of human character [44]. Moreover, doing justice means caring about people's vulnerabilities [44], which is about empathy. Justice and compassion are not distant from each other [50]. Also, emotions have constantly challenged practical reason [38].

“Truly universal human rights”

In the 21st century, we need “truly universal human rights” instead of “neoliberal human rights” to substantiate the human right to health. It can be argued that neoliberalism hijacked the human rights agenda, e.g., Manfredi [51] indicates that the entanglements between the human rights movement and neoliberalism or an amalgamation of neoliberal logic with human rights in specific contexts have been formed in ways that transform both concepts.

The notion of universality of human rights implies that entitlements and basic needs are universal and inherent in all human beings. Universal human rights are inherent to all indivisible and encompass positive-social and economic human rights and are premised on the acceptance of the universal moral human dignity (which is not accepted by neoliberal capitalism, e.g., Whyte [23] argues that “neoliberals broke decisively with the conception of equality enshrined in the declarations of the rights of man”).

It is crucial to what human rights are in the process of becoming. “The power of human rights lies in their enduring promise that a more just world can emerge from a sustained and creative struggle through, against, and at the margins of states, laws, and institutions” [52]. Human rights motivate institutions to respond when the fundamental components of what makes life worth living are threatened, and in the case of health, threats can arise from both human action (and inaction) and natural forces [53]. On the other hand, health threats do not stop at political borders, and therefore, the commitment to protect health and the duty to respond must transcend national boundaries [53].

Therefore, “unless health and health care are wholeheartedly accepted as human rights rather than commodities, failed efforts to address the root causes of systemic inequalities under capitalism will continue” [54]. In other words, health status as a positive human right [53] has to be strongly established. Moreover, “the human right to health can and to be a weapon against the structural violence that forces so many of the world's poorest people into illness and premature death and a political instrument to help us combat global health crises as they inevitably arise” [55]. As such, accepting the right to health as a fundamental human right and making access to health care a human right pose significant challenges to neoliberal capitalism.

Empathy is necessary to unlock the potential of the universalistic nature of human rights

The hardening of the personality and disregard for the needs of other people (even disregard for the dignity of other people) are rooted in “philosophical apathy” and “capitalist coldness” [38]. Overall, we can connect the problems related to the conceptualization of the broad understanding of health and legitimization of the human right to health (and health care) with (1) the lack of philosophical justification of the human right to health (and, in general, human rights), (2) “lop-sided reason” of positivistic epistemology of social sciences, manifested in the lack of using of the concept of empathy in legitimizing the universality of human rights, and (3) “capitalistic coldness”. However, empathy plays a crucial role in understanding the universality of human rights. In general, emotions “are to play a role in contemporary theory and the defense of human rights” [38].

This paper echoes the position of Yamin [1], who emphasizes that defining health as a human rights issue is closely and inextricably linked to how we understand our suffering and the suffering of others. Taking suffering seriously also means challenging “narrow conceptions” of rights — what they say about justice and how we live in this world.

Specifically, in contexts of great inequality and deprivation, taking rights seriously requires taking suffering seriously. Taking suffering seriously means rising to the challenge of reshaping our approaches to health and human rights [1]. Other’s suffering can be understood through empathy, which is crucial to legitimizing and developing the human rights to health and health care. On the other hand, critical realist scholars [44,46], who criticize the positivistic social sciences, emphasize that we must acknowledge that our connection to the world is based on concern and that reason is not beyond emotions.

Empathy is crucial to unlocking the potential of the universalistic nature of human rights to underpin the conceptual foundations of the human right to health. First, the fundamental idea of human rights, respect for universal human dignity, can

be perceived through empathy. Second, empathy is indispensable in allowing people to perceive and accept the human right to health (and health care) through the prism of the equality dimension of human rights, expressed in the fact that they are universal and non-negotiable [56]. The defining universalist feature of human rights is found in the formula “everyone” - all people should enjoy these entitlements. Their counterpart is privilege, the “rights” of only a particular group of individuals [56].

Third, empathy is the key to recognizing that every human life is infinitely valuable. When people trust their perceptions and empathize with others, they want to take care of each other. They also do not want anyone to be discriminated against or dehumanized [37]. So not only can the human rights to health and health care be based on empathy, but empathy also leads us to see injustice in health care as something that cannot be tolerated; as Dr. Martin Luther King [57] emphasized, injustice in health care is the most shocking and inhumane of all forms of injustice. In summary, the universalistic nature of human rights and the human right to health (and health care) can be substantiated by empathy.

All in all, in theorizing how to develop the human right to health, the arguments for the need to accept the concept of care as a human being's relationship to the world [44,46,47] and in parallel to assume that human rights need not only rationality but also emotions, specifically empathy [1,38] are crucial. Ultimately, we need empathy and heart to understand the universal human dignity and social determination of health that capitalism does not possess.

CONCLUSION

Throughout this paper, we have critically examined the human right to health, elucidating the profound challenges of capitalist structures and the dominant positivist epistemology. Our analysis has underscored that health transcends physical and mental well-being, significantly intertwining with social welfare and power dynamics.

The neoliberal agenda, with its emphasis on privatization and market-driven policies, has been shown to erode public health systems, diminish social protections, and widen health disparities across global populations. This trend, starkly illuminated by the recent COVID-19 pandemic, calls for an urgent reassessment of health as a fundamental human right rather than a commodity subject to market forces.

Moreover, we have argued that the positivist approach in social sciences—characterized by its rigid adherence to empirical and logical methodologies—fails to capture health's complex, multifaceted nature. By its very nature, this approach sidelines moral and ethical considerations, which are crucial to understanding and implementing comprehensive health rights.

Empathy emerges as a vital component in reconceptualizing health rights. It bridges the gap between isolated empirical observations and the lived experiences of individuals, fostering a more inclusive understanding of health that aligns with the universality of human rights. Empathy facilitates a deeper understanding of the social determinants of health and enables the formulation of more compassionate and effective health policies.

In light of these discussions, policymakers, scholars, and health practitioners must strive toward a holistic approach to health. This involves advocating for policies informed by a critical realist perspective, which acknowledges the role of empirical evidence and broader socioeconomic contexts. Such an approach should aim to dismantle the barriers erected by neoliberal capitalism and ensure that healthcare systems serve the collective needs of all rather than the interests of a privileged few.

As we progress, the global community must commit to a robust dialogue and concerted action to reframe health care as a universal human right. This involves theoretical reconceptualization and tangible changes in how health policies are formulated and implemented. Only through a concerted effort to integrate empathy, social justice, and a broader understanding of health can we hope to achieve a truly inclusive and equitable global health system.

In conclusion, this paper calls for a paradigm shift in understanding and enacting health rights. As researchers, policymakers, and global citizens, we must foster a dialogical approach that values empathy and inclusivity, ensuring that health care is recognized and realized as a fundamental human right, integral to the dignity of every individual.

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